

Know Common Spices of Bharat

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Abstract:- Bharat is not only the largest producer, rather Bharat has also the highest numbers of consumer of spices. Spices are nothing but whole or ground form, that are obtained from natural resources i.e. different plants or vegetables and which are useful for imparting flavour, aroma and pungency to foods. It is believed that they enhance the shelf life of foods. It is really astonishing that spices used by the people of different states of Bharat are almost same and so it reflects another smell of integrity among the people of our country. People of Bharat, particularly tribal communities are using spices to get relief from different ailments. Traditional use of spices is working also in few diseases practically.

Keywords:- Spices, Bharat, Uses, Medicinal Prospects.

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Are you favouring mother's preparation? Are you fond of food from restaurants? Do you prefer street foods? Whatever foods, we are eating or enjoying, all are special for their own taste and flavor due to the use of different spices. Spices are nothing but whole or ground form, that are obtained from natural resources i.e. different plants or vegetables and which are useful for imparting flavour, aroma and pungency to foods. These are also demandable items in nutraceutical industries. It is believed that they enhance the shelf life of foods. Different parts of the plants / trees or vegetables are used as spices such as fruits, stigma, bark, seeds, leaves, kernel, aril, bulbs, berries etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the ancient time, Bharat has been famous for varieties of spices, also known as the home of Spices, and spices draw attraction for their exotic flavour, taste and medicinal values. Around the world about more than 70 types of spices are grown. It is really a wonderful information that Bharat is not only the largest producer,

II. COMMON SPICES OF BHARAT

It is really astonishing that spices used by the people of different states of Bharat are almost same and so it reflects another smell of integrity among the people of our country. People of Bharat, particularly tribal communities are using spices to get relief from different ailments. Traditional use of spices is working also in few diseases practically.

Table-1 : Common Spices Used By The People of Bharat²

Sl. No.	Name of the States	Common spices used by the people of the respective states of Bharat	Popular dishes prepared by using noted spices
1	Andra Pradesh & Telengana	Ginger, Garlic, Cardamom, Cuminseeds, Cloves, Mint, Saffron, Turmeric, Jeera, Bay leaves, Black cumin, onion, chilli, cinnamon, mace, mint, saffron, coriander, lemon juice, fenugreek, sesame	Hyderabadi biryani, Mirchi salan, Kodikura, Gongura pickle, Kajjikayalu
2	Arunachal Pradesh	Asafoetida, Turmeric, Cumin, Coriander, mastard seed, chilli, curry leaves, onion, ginger, garlic, tamarind, sesame, capsicum	Dosakai pappu, Simple chicken, Rohu fish kalia, Pulihora, Prawn jhal freji, Kulcha, Biriyani
3	Assam	Ginger, Garlic, Cinnamon, Cardamom, Turmeric, chilli, bayleaf, black pepper, cumin seeds, cloves, onion, polygonum, fenugreek, lemon grass, coriander leaves, curry leaves, mustard seed, sesame seed, tamarind, raisins	Masor tenga jol, Pitha(s), Egg soap recipe, Tomato oambal / chutney, Assam laksa, Poorahaah, Mambooshoot, Pumpkin oambal, Cabbage kofta curry, Fish fried rice
4	Bihar	Ajwain, ginger, green chilli, coriander, lemon, elaichi, bay leaf, red dried chilli, mustard seeds, cumin, turmeric, onion, garlic, clove, cardamom, saffron	Litti, Khaja, Anarsa
5	Chattisgarh	Raisins, elaichi, turmeric, bay leaf, capsicum, cumin, chilli, clove, cardamom	Kusli, Sabudana kichuri, Khurma, Lavang lata
6	Dadra and Nagar Haveli	Cardamom, cloves, garlic, coriander, green chilli, onion, garlic, lemon, pepper	Paunk ka salad
7	Delhi	Cumin, coriander, bay leaves, ginger, green chilli, fennel, turmeric, garlic, cardamom, black pepper, cloves, onion, garlic, nutmeg, anise, lemon juice,	Delhi chat, Paratha, Cholay and bhature, Nihari, Seekh kebab, Haleem, Korma, Mutton pulao, Moti-choor laddoo, Kulfi

		mace, saffron, pista, cumin	and falooda, Sohan halwa, Murgh makhni, Tandoori chicken
8	Goa	Onion, chilli, cardamom, garlic, black pepper, cumin seeds, turmeric, coriander, clove, black pepper, fennel seeds, nutmeg, anise, curry leaves, lemon juice, cinnamon, nutmeg, mace, peppercorn, ginger	Mutton vindaloo, Lamb xacuti, Bebinca, Prawn balchao
9	Gujrat	Garlic, cloves, chilli, turmeric, onion, coriander, cumin, jeera, asafoetida, fenugreek, lentil, black pepper, methi leaves, lemon juice, curry leaves, sesame, mustard seed, asafoetida, ginger, methi	Thepla, Suji dhokla, Dhokla, Khandvi, Handvo, Rice panki, Dhansak, Nankhatai
10	Haryana	Asafoetida, chilli, garlic, clove, cardamom, garlic, onion, tej pata, jeera, cinnamon, bay leaf, turmeric, ginger, coriander, cumin, lime juice, black pepper, heeng, saffron, pista	Cholia, Namkeen chach, Mathatha, Bajra khichdi, Rabadi
11	Himachal Pradesh	Chilli, clove, cardamom, garlic, onion, tej pata, jeera, aniseed, asafoetida, turmeric, cinnamon, fennel, cayenne, peppercorn, bay leaf, cilantro, black pepper, coriander, cumin, ajwain, mustard seed, dill	Sidu, Marda, Bhatura, Kullu trout
12	Jammu&Kashmir	Ginger, clove, cardamom, cinnamon, coriander, garlic, cumin, onion, fenugreek, fennel, black pepper, curry leaves, peppercorn, tej pata, turmeric, spinach, bay leaf	Rogan josh, Tabak maaz, Gustaba, Dum aloo, Haak saag, Kashmiri roast yakhni
13	Jharkhand	Ginger, ajwain, fennel, green chilli, coriander, lemon, elaichi, bay leaf, red dried chilli, mustard seeds, cumin, turmeric, onion, garlic, clove, cardamom, saffron, heeng, raisins, asafoetida	Dhuska, Thekua, Pua, Marua roti, Dal peethi, Dalpitha, Bhindi masala, Rice cheela, Dal pitha
14	Karnataka	Ginger, clove, cardamom, cinnamon, coriander, garlic, cumin, onion, fenugreek, fennel, black pepper, curry leaves, peppercorn, saffron, pista, raisins, mustard seed, tamarind, lime juice	Vangi bhath, Bisi belabath, Kesari bhath, Mysore pak, Sambar, Konkani grilled fish, Kane rava fry, Rava fried fish, Fish moilee, Coorg pandi curry, Ghorikai uppakari
15	Kerala	Chilli, cumin, onion, ginger, turmeric, clove, onion, garlic, pepper, curry leaves, sesame, mustard seed, clove, pepper, coriander, cumin	Avial, Malabar parotha, Neipathiri, Jackfruit upkari, Drumstick mango, Mango chammundi, Kovakkari upperi, Eggplant mango curry, Chicken pirattal, Coconut milk mushroom gravy, Zucchini olan, Coconut pudding, Pumpkin cucumber mulagoottal
16	Madhya Pradesh	Cardamom, clove, coriander, nutmeg, clove, Cinnamon, ginger, garlic, onion, bay leaf, asafoetida, raisins, chilli, cumin, mace, bay leaf, saffron, lemon juice	Lapsi, Indori puri palak ki, Kusli, Cashew barfi, Lavang lata, Pilaf with peas and carrots, Jalebi, Bhopali kebab, Bafla, Bhutte ki khees
17	Maharashtra	Cardamom, onion, ajwain, jeera, onion, coriander, curry leaves, turmeric, saffron, pista, chilli, dhania pata, mustard seeds	Shirkhan, Thalipeeth, Vada pav, Modak
18	Manipur	Chilli, onion, turmeric, clove, cumin, ginger, garlic, onion, coriander, asafoetida, elaichi, kala jeera	Iromba, Kongsoi, Soibum thongba, Sareng thonga, Chak angouba, Sana thongba, Kamen ashinba athooma, Aloo kangmet, Ngaatoiba thongba, Mairensaag
19	Meghalaya	Bay leaf, ginger, onion, turmeric, cilantro, black pepper, sesame, raisins, saffron, pista, clove, garlic, caraway, lemon juice	Jadoh, Spicy asian slaw, Shir sewain, Aamras ke malai aloo
20	Mizoram	Coriander, onion, turmeric, peppercorn, chilli, polygonum, lemon grass, bay leaf, fenugreek, aniseed, lemon juice, tamarind, cumin, clove, mint, lettuce	Misa mach poora, Mizoram laksa stock, Dal and eggs, Panch phoran taarkari, Thukpa, Laksa stock, Koat pitha
21	Nagaland	Turmeric, onion, coriander, peppercorn, fenugreek, chilli, turmeric, onion, ginger, clove, garlic, bay leaf, black pepper, cumin	Misa mach poora, Poora nachh, Bamboo shoot fry, Poora haah, Fish fried rice, Dal-egg curry

22	Odisha	Clove, ginger, garlic, onion, cardamom, saffron, pista	Fish orly, Khirmohan, Rasabali, Chenna poda
23	Puduchery	Clove, turmeric, cumin, curry leaves, fenugreek, garlic, onion, chilli, mustard seed	Kadugu yerra
24	Punjab	Clove, chilli, ginger, garlic, turmeric, onion, maize, asafoetida, black pepper, fenugreek, jeera, cumin, cinnamon, coriander, cardamom, mint, bay leaf, peppercorn, ajwain, mustard seed, mint, spinach, sesame, lemon juice	Makai-ki-roti, Sarson-ka-saag, Rajma and chawal, Punjabi kadhi pakora, Aloo amritsari, Dal maharani, Mooli paratha, Palakwali dal, Lobia masala, Vegetable pulao, Sukhi chana dal, Hariyali tikki, Karah parshad, Karela masaledar, Khoya matar, Chole and bhature, Amritsar machhli, Amritsari aloo kulcha, Masala chop, Achari muttan, Palak gosht, Murg kali mirch, Murg makkai, Lassi, Gulab lassi, Meethi lassi
25	Rajasthan	Clove, chilli, turmeric, bay leaf, , coriander, cumin, asafoetida, tamarind, amchur, clove, turmeric, cardamom, ginger, garlic, onion, black pepper, mint, fennelsaffron, pista, ajwain, chilli	Dal-baati churma, , Lal-maas, Gatte ka pulao, Pyaz kachori, Ghevar, Kalakand, Ker-sangari
26	Sikkim	Chilli, fenugreek, ginger, garlic, onion, coriander, fenugreek, pepper, turmeric clove, cardamom	Momos, Thukpa, Gundruk and sinki soup, Phagshapa, Sael roti
27	Tamilnadu	Chilli, onion, spinach, turmeric, coriander, curry leaves, ginger, onion, mustard seeds, cumin, fenugreek, asafoetida, tamarind, lemon juice, clove, cardamom, cinnamon, black pepper	Appam, Keerai dosa, Masala dosa, Rava dosa, Idli, Sambhar, Chettinad chicken, pongal
28	Tripura	Chilli (green & red), turmeric, ginger, pista, saffron, onion, garlic, cumin, mustard seeds, panchforan, methi	Chakhwi, Gudak, Macher jhol, Kaju badam tacos
29	Uttar Pradesh	Chilli, coriander, cumin, ginger, garlic, mint, onion, jaiphal, clove, turmeric, cinnamon, cardamom, fennel, pepper, saffron, anise, lemon juice, elaichi, raisin, black pepper	Shami kabab, Awadhi mutton biryani, Aloo kachori, Halwa, Banarasi chaat
30	Uttara Khand	Turmeric, coriander, cumin, chilli, garlic, black pepper, asafoetida, cilantro, mustard seed, spinach, clove, onion	Aloo gutke, Kaapa, Jhangore kheer, Chainsoo
31	West Bengal	Mustard seeds, Clove, chilli, turmeric, ginger, onion, cardamom, cinnamon, turmeric, elaichi, bay leaf, garlic, clove, bay leaves, elaichi, cumin, raisin, lemon juice	Bhetki macher paturi, Bhapa ilish, Chingri malaikari, Kosha mangsho, Aloo posto, Rasgulla, Mishti doi

III. MEDICINAL PROSPECTS AND CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Commonly used spices in different foodstuffs are having broad spectrum of bio-functions due to presence of different bioactive compounds, which may provide promising health benefits to our body and to give relief from many common disorders. Scientific approaches are there to establish the health benefits of spices. During pandemic due to corona virus, spices such as turmeric, ginger, clove, pepper, cinnamon, cardamom were widely used in different food preparation and formulation like kadha, herbal tea, masala tea etc., which played a major role to arrest or reduce the effect of the viruses. In few of the cases, active ingredients are evaluated. Parts used as spices, active components reported, if any, and the health benefits of few common spices are presented below:-

➤ CLOVE

Cloves are the dried flower buds of the *Syzygium aromaticum* tree. It was used as traditional medicine for curing tooth decay, digestive issues, bad breath, aphrodisiac. It contains volatile oil with Eugenol, vitamin C, vitamin E, flavonoids, gallic acid, tanins, triterpene, glycosides, eugenin etc. It has action against few microorganisms. It relieves toothaches, sore gums, mouth ulcers.^{1,3,4}

➤ CINNAMON

Cinnamon bark is used and commonly known as Kalmi-Dalchini and is obtained from the trees of *Cinnmorum zeylanicum* or *Cinnamomum verum* of the family Lauraceae. It contains volatile oil with Cinnamic aldehyde or cinnamaldehyde, Phenols especially eugenol, Cuminaldehyde and benzaldehyde, terpenes like pinene, phellandrene, carophyllene, along with ketones, isobutyric acid, alcohols and esters, tannins(phlobatannins), mucilage, calcium oxalate and mannitol. It is used in the treatment of toothache, dental hygiene, colds and flu, indigestion.^{1,4}

➤ **GARLIC**

Garlic is the ripe bulb of the plant *Allium sativum*, family Liliaceae. Chemical constituents are found- alliin (exerts unpleasant smell), volatile oil with allin, allyl propyl disulphide and diallyl disulphide, carbohydrates, fats, proteins, mucilage, Minerals-Calcium, copper, iron, phosphorus and potassium. Garlic is used in amoebic dysentery, indigestion, Hypertension, cold, flu, fever, sore throat, as anthelmintic, insomnia.^{1,4}

➤ **TURMERIC**

The rhizome of *Curcuma longa* plant is most popularly used as Turmeric, family - Zingiberaceae, also known as haldi and it contains essential oil and the coloring substance curcumin, phenolic bioactive compound – curcuminoid, sodium salts of curcumin & curcuminoids. It has uses as anti-oxidant, antimicrobial, antiseptic & antibacterial, blood purifier.^{1,5}

➤ **BLACK PEPPER**

Black pepper or pepper is the fruits of perennial climbing vine - *Piper nigrum*, family- Piperaceae. It contains alkaloids - Piperine & Piperettine, volatile oil, Essential oil consists of Terpenes, Sesquiterpenes, Piperolides, Propenylphenols, Amides, Neolignans, Lignans, Flavonoids, Steroids, fiber, protein, starch, Potassium, Calcium, Manganese, Iron and vitamins K and C. Black pepper is believed to prevent cancer with turmeric, helps in good digestion, helps in breaking down the proteins by releasing hydrochloric acid, prevents Cold and cough.⁴

➤ **BAYLEAF**

Bay leaf commonly is obtained from *Laurus nobilis*, has distinctive flavor and fragrance, contains essential oils consisting eucalyptol, terpenes, terpinyl acetate, sesquiterpenes, methyleugenol, α - and β -pinenes, phellandrene, linalool, geraniol, terpineol, lauric acid, vitamin A, vitamin B6, and vitamin C. It supports healthy immune system, helps to cure upset stomach, helps to relieve sinus pressure or stuffy nose, treat menstrual problem.^{1,4}

➤ **CORIANDER**

It is the dried ripe seeds of *Coriandrum sativum*, family- Umbelliferae, also known as Dhaniya, Dhane or Cilantro. Whole parts are edible and mostly fresh leaves and dried seeds are used traditionally. The coriander fruit contains volatile oil with Linalool, coriandrylacetate, geraniol, γ -terpenene, esters, limonene. It is also rich for flavonoids, coumarins, isocoumarins, pthalides, phenolic acids, Fats, Proteins, vitamin A. It is useful as analgesic, antispasmodic, carminative, deodorant, digestive, relieves cramps, useful in cold and flu.^{1,4}

➤ **GINGER**

Root of *Zingiber officinale* is used as ginger, family- Zingiberaceae. It contains phenolic compounds- gingerol shogaol, paradols, and terpene. It is also used in different beverages like tea, lime juice. It is useful in Cold & coughs,

improves the blood supply, keeps heart muscles healthy, useful in diabetes.⁵

➤ **CARDAMOM**

Cardamom, the Queen of spice, is the fruit of *Ellettaria cardamomum*, family- Zingiberaceae. It contains volatile oil with cineole, terpinyl acetate, pinene, sabinene and pborneol. It is helpful in flatulent indigestion, increases appetite, treats anorexia, aids in digestion, prevents nausea and vomiting, boosts energy in metabolism, helps to burn body-fat.⁵

➤ **CHILLI**

Chilli, the frequently used spice in our daily life, is the fruit of commonly available *Capsicum annum*. Chillies are having different size, shapes and color. The red color of chillies is due to the presence of capsanthin, a carotenoid pigment. The pungency of chillies is due to the presence of alkaloid capsaicin. Green chilli has Vitamin C & vitamin A. Capsicum oleoresin is used to get relief from pain, swelling and inflammation. It has use as a stimulant to release ptyalin in saliva, which helps in digestion.^{1,5}

➤ **CARAWAY**

Caraway (from *Carum carvi*, family- Apiaceae) seeds stimulate milk flow in nursing mothers. Limonene obtained from caraway may reduce cancer risk. Caraway also helps in digestion. Its volatile oil contains D-carvone. Fixed oil contains fatty acids – oleic acid, linoleic acid, petroselinic acid, palmitic acid.⁵

➤ **Cumin**

It is the fruit of *Cuminum cyminum*, family – Apiaceae. Due to presence of antioxidants, it has anticancer effects. Cumin contains volatile oil with cuminaldehyde, cymene, terpenoids, vitamin E, B vitamins, iron, magnesium, manganese.^{1,5}

➤ **Mustard seeds**

They contain allyl isothiocyanates, which inhibits the growth of the cancer cells. The seeds may be obtained from Brassica nigra or Brassica juncea or Sinapis alba.^{1,5}

➤ **Nutmeg and mace**

Both come from same plant – *Myristica fragrans*. Nutmeg is the shelled seed and mace its hull. The volatile oil contains myristicin may cause hallucination. Eugenol helps to cure heart disease. It has also antibacterial property, particularly against *E. coli*.^{1,5}

➤ **Onion**

Onion is the bulb of commonly available *Allium cepa*. It contains flavonoids, anthocyanin pigments, B vitamins, vitamin C, minerals etc. It may lower elevated blood cholesterol, reduce the ability of the blood to clot. It has mild antibacterial effect. Sulfur compounds may block carcinogens. It reduces hair fall also.^{1,5}

IV. CONCLUSION

Spices in Bharat are nowadays attracting the world population. Very interestingly, in social media also cooking and use of spices in different dishes are one of the point of attraction of interested people to visit different websites / social sites. The presentation of preparation of different food items along with its recepie and description of moments for addition of spices are important to draw attention of large population and it would be more attractive as when a story to be narrated corelating the taste of dishes along with detailed description of therapeutic uses of spices. However, research works may be carried out more to explore the therapeutic uses of spices of Bharat and to report the chemical constituents present in those spices.

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